

The Impact of Covid-19 on Human Rights and Individual Health: The Perspective of International Cooperation Limitations

JOY OKUNDIA

*Department of International Business Administration
Faculty of Communications and Environment, Rhine-Waal University, Germany*

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Abstract – The coronavirus pandemic has distorted the economy in all areas of life because of the spread of the virus, causing significant harm to health and individual human rights. However, nations are taking desperate actions to limit its spread and adverse consequences. Some of these actions include setting up quarantine policies, and at the same time, countries are turning to self-help instead of cooperating with other nations to combat the pandemic. Moreover, developing a vaccine to curb this viral infection has prompted an imbalance in international relations. Furthermore, people blame international leaders for their conflicting actions, which usually challenges global struggles to mitigate the pandemic that affects human rights and health (Pevehouse, 2020). Thus, the author carries out current research to evaluate the impact of international relations theories on the relationship between nations. Conclusively, the findings indicated that the implication of Coronavirus could influence international relations positively in terms of helping each other to come up with solutions and adversely when other nations are uncooperative.

Keywords – *Covid-19, vaccines, health, human right, international relations theories*

1 Introduction

The word pandemic emanates from Greek, in which the pan means all and demic people. The globally recognised definition popularly refers to a widespread transmissible disease outbreak like a wide geographical extension, the spread of virus, novelty, and high attack rates severely affecting many populations. However, history documented significant disease outbreaks and pandemics, like the Spanish Flu, Hong Kong Flu, SARS, Ebola, and Zika (Qiu et al., 2017). It is imperative to evaluate the impact of the Covid- 19 pandemic on international relations theory during the author’s research of this paper, thereby profiling solutions that will mitigate against cooperation among nations. Hence, giving room for the reader to see how this international theory helps during the crisis imbalance.

*Corresponding author

✉ joyokundia@hsrw.org

I. The COVID-19 pandemic

The official publication of the Covid-19 outbreak in Wuhan City in China's Hubei Province set the world on another platform. Even though the first cases were reported in December 2019 (hence the name COVID-19), it was barely on the 30th of January 2020; the World Health Organization (WHO) announced a global public health crisis over the outbreak of the novel Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2). In this manner, the WHO affirmed it to be of person-to-person transmission from many different cases outside China (Nguyen, Duong Bang, and Wolff, 2020). According to Lauer et al. (2020), this virus has an incubation period from two to fourteen days, wherein its symptoms are shortness of breath, sore throat, diarrhoea, dry cough, and fever. Another critical thing to recall is that to decelerate the spread of the virus, many countries such as China declared a national lockdown followed by Italy using similar measures, thereby positively or adversely affecting millions of people (Nguyen, Duong Bang, and Wolff, 2020). In addition, the first steps to stop the spreading of the infection were unsuccessful after WHO declared the pandemic of the Coronavirus. Notwithstanding, the widespread of the pandemic worsened the health and led to a high volume of unemployment, wherein political leaders and residents in certain nations did not follow the essential preventive measures. For example, mask-wearing and social distancing—causing the spread of infections to distort the entire globe (Kwang-Yeong, 2021).

According to Brands and Gavin (2020), public health specialists cautioned about the risks of viral pandemics that cut across borders and the requirement for active national and international reactions. Considering this, both the Johns Hopkins Centre for Health Security and the Kissinger Centre for Global Affairs coordinated separate movements that featured how significantly a fast-moving virus can imperil the international system. However, the world did not respond effectively when the crisis started as the population did not heed the warnings. For instance, the virus affected the United States, with more than five million affirmed cases and still counting with the spread not under control. Despite this, scientists and epidemiologists are making a meaningful effort in developing vaccines to curb the pandemic (Brands and Gavin, 2020). The covid -19 pandemic may be exceptional in terms of the pressure of the health crisis and has pushed nations to take considerable actions. Significantly, Covid-19 showed the limitations of international relations cooperation in addressing such outbreaks. Further, the pandemic (in terms of the spread of the virus and new cases) and the financial downturn adversely affect most nations and, at the same time, make it challenging for the world to establish a coordinated reaction that will diminish the effects of Coronavirus (Beteringhe et al., 2020).

II. The objective of the study

In essence, this paper scrutinises how the pandemic and governmental restrictions have affected individual well-being and human rights while limiting the spread of the infection. Moreover, the author will clarify some international relation theories utilised to reduce the effect of the crisis and thereby present an analogy to explain if nations will generally cooperate or not. In addition, the paper emphasises why developed countries tend to have more access to the vaccine than developing/emerging nations, leading to inequality in vaccines distribution. In addition, this paper is applicable for international relations organisations and people keen to know more about the current issues. The author utilised information from reliable sources.

I. Research Question

While x-raying the subject matter, the author has been able to ask the question: How does the Coronavirus pandemic affect international relations among nations and its impacts on human rights and the health of the people?

II. Outline of Chapters

In this section of the paper, the author gathered data on existing published literature using textbooks, scientific articles, reliable and authentic websites to understand the topic better. Moreover, the author will emphasise how limitations to decrease the Covid-19 virus affect human rights and individual health. Furthermore, the author will reveal a detailed outline of vaccine development and its disparity in distribution during the pandemic. Followed by the role of international cooperation in times of Coronavirus pandemic utilising international relations theories. The term paper comprises the following chapters: Introduction, literature review, findings, discussion, and conclusion.

IV. Limitation of the Study

The academic paper is a compilation of existing global circumstances wherein the article does not have quantitative depth. Moreover, the author's idea is that data fluctuates continuously given the changing description of the Covid-19 issues; therefore, it is unnecessary. Besides, the paper does not utilise direct quotes to backing claims since the author did not cite any of those directly; however, the author rendered references to several authors in the discussions.

2 Literature Review

Health is a state of mental, and social well-being, which is the highest attainable standard of fundamental rights of each human being irrespective of individual differences (WHO, 2006). Unfortunately, the crisis between 1918 and 2019 also led to similar pandemic-management strategies

with Covid-19. Regardless of a commitment to human rights and health, international leaders scrutinised the WHO and International Organisations based on how they managed the crisis and human rights in the early stage of the pandemic. Notably, governments have mainly supported similar pandemic procedures, like isolation, quarantine, school, and shop closures, as well as bans on public social events in light of public health authorities' guidance (Wong and Wong, 2020). Gruskin et al. (2012) indicated that people live in a world where most states firmly acknowledge common liberties; therein, international organisations focus on relieving the pandemic's negative effect on human rights. In addition, health freedom cannot be typically achieved without the adequate protection of other rights, wherein COVID-19 disrupts the global run, showing that individual-level economic well-being is inadequate to alleviate the profound effects of the novel virus (World Health Organisation, 2020).

II. The Challenges of COVID-19 Vaccine Distribution

Some scholars utilised international relation theories to describe specific outcomes (Toebes 2015) highlighted that the pandemic had been an area of less concentration in the view of global politics and human rights. Then again, the Covid-19 pandemic brings into sharp relief the inconsistent problems tolerated by front-line workers in low-paying assistance occupations. These workers bear great danger in relating with people during periods in which the movement is constrained and have their rights restricted due to their jobs in supporting communities in their society. For example, nurses, doctors, logistics workers, and people whose social rights have been affected during this pandemic deserve better remuneration for their job well done. Moreover, people are more liberal about limiting their rights, especially in a situation that will negatively affect human health, such as restrictions on freedom of movement, assembly and more tedious policy decisions, like isolation. Since health and security are interconnected, it is vital to think about protection with regards to safety, including human security, even if this conceptualisation has its borders (Rubenstein and DeCamp 2020). In the current pandemic triggered by Covid-19, people perceived immunisation through vaccination as a general health priority. Since then, several scientists and researchers have continuously worked hard to develop vaccines to curb Coronavirus. Therefore, this has a significant economic effect because new technological programs and innovative techniques are needed to achieve vaccines (Calina et al., 2020; Hyder et al., 2021). Moreover, Guidry et al. (2021) claimed that few vaccine competitors enter the market to attain global immunity against this virus. Yet, there is a major problem impeding the fulfilment of this purpose: the unequal distribution of COVID-19 amongst developed and developing/emerging countries. To begin with, BNN Bloomberg (2020) claimed that Canada tends to be the highest per capita hoard of the eight vaccines developed, wherein the county has reserved

enough for roughly five complete immunisations per resident. Besides that, the United States has about four vaccinations requested per capita.

Subsequently, Dyer (2020) claimed that the United Kingdom ordered enough for around three vaccinations which are 5,7 vaccine doses per head. Consequently, several low-income nations have little to no acquisition of these vaccines of their own. They are highly dependent on The Covid-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility (Covax) program—a collaboration involving the World Health Organisation, United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund, and the World Bank, among other non-profit organisations. Meanwhile, the program has secured roughly 700 million doses to vaccinate just ten per cent of the population in 67 nations. Hyder et al. (2021) indicated that the gap between accessible vaccines and immunised individuals raises anxieties around the manufacturing of vaccines and the rate at which countries and organisations cooperate. At the same time, the approach nations are utilising during the COVID-19 vaccination demands to address critical moral and social fairness concerns. Sawal et al. (2021) argued that the Chief General of the WHO expressed that vaccine fairness tends to be a great challenge nowadays, wherein people expected to support equally fail to do the right thing. The authors also stated that out of the 832 million vaccine dosages administered globally, only 82 per cent are already dispatched to developed nations. In contrast, just 0,2 per cent have arrived in low-income nations. It means that one in four people is vaccinated in developed countries, whereas this proportion drops to one in every 500 individuals in underprivileged nations. All things considered, the threat or challenge is that vulnerable groups will not get the vaccine first, or even at the ideal time, and will be the last to be protected, further intensifying existing health disparity (Hyder et al., 2021). Consequently, vaccine nationalism—nations pushing hard to access it— can extend the disaster, further decreasing the global economy. Coupled with, during the start of the Coronavirus, nations embraced a nationalistic approach where they restricted the exportation of numerous clinical supplies such as ventilators and protective masks to keep them for their countries only. Subsequently, the Coronavirus pandemic has also highlighted the unsophisticated disparities that have consistently existed among developed and developing/emerging countries. It is not only triggering humanitarian anguishes but also leading to a vast economic problem such as poverty of immunisation, and therefore they tend to lack them as long as some people continue to stay unprotected (Bolcato et al., 2021; Hyder et al., 2021). Moreover, several aspects may cause a significant challenge to vaccine distribution in developing/emerging nations, such as low levels of education with the poor socio-economic status of the resident living in some of these countries, consequently influencing the acceptance of the Coronavirus vaccine.

In addition, some developing/emerging nations located in geographically less accessible areas tend to have a significant challenge for fair vaccine distribution because they have inadequate access to vaccination services. For that reason, it is difficult for these nations, further prompting

disproportion in COVID-19 vaccine circulation. Moreover, many countries that are financially capable of procuring vast amounts of vaccine doses are taking advantage of the system. Countries like Brazil and Indonesia already arranged to acquire millions of COVID-19 vaccine dosages under phase-three trial, contributing to the critical lack of vaccines (Callaway, 2020). The lack of suitable methods of transporting and storing the vaccines at low temperatures also creates a significant challenge as many developing/emerging countries lack infrastructures in which people do not have access to electricity. Most developing/emerging countries lack sophisticated research laboratories, government funds, planning, vaccine-producing guidelines, and programs that help facilitate effective vaccine development. Hence, regardless of approving the production of COVID-19 vaccines in some nations, it will not help resolve vaccine distribution disparities due to lack of infrastructure and other political challenges (Acharya et al., 2021; Binagwaho et al., 2021).

In a nutshell, the broader accessibility of the Coronavirus vaccine in developing/emerging nations will play a key role in accomplishing a global immunity against the virus. Ultimately, health is a fundamental human right, and the distribution of COVID-19 vaccines ought to be regarded as a worldwide public good instead of as commercial interests accessible to those nations with enough money to acquire the vaccines. It is vital to note that vaccine accessibility, medicals, and health machinery are fundamental to human rights. Follows by the right to develop and distribute the vaccines and the right to benefit from all the best available scientific advancement necessary to the highest possible standard of health (United Nations, 2020). Also, Acharya et al. (2021); Binagwaho et al. (2021) suggested that vaccine distribution demands global cooperation, wherein reputable organisations such as United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), WHO need to address these issues, which also requires an immediate solution. These organisations need to assist developing/emerging nations gain quick access and equal distribution of the COVID-19 vaccine to everyone.

III. The Role of International Cooperation in Times of Covid-19 Pandemic

Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) has shown to be one of the terrifying global health challenges the world has ever encountered since the Spanish Flu, which have revealed the rate at which nations cooperate during uncertainties. For example, instead of working together to strategise on sharing knowledge and boosting the overall accessibility of medical equipment globally, there have been bans on exportations, travelling, and beggar-thy-neighbour bidding wars (Brown and Susskind, 2020). Besides, for nations to cooperate to foster a novel effective vaccine, vaccine nationalism has replaced it. Every country unilaterally seeks separate research programs, even trying to secure research workers from other territories. Nonetheless, there has been inadequate cooperation in offering support to developing/emerging nations with weaker states that are incapable of efficiently monitoring the spread of the virus alone. Moreover, after the world war, the United States decides to act unilaterally,

referring to America First. This attitude is already influencing other countries, discouraging them from cooperating and responding efficiently in this pandemic time (Brown and Susskind, 2021).

The author uses the Realism approach to explain the recent pandemic outbreak, thus addressing the pandemic issues and predicting the future outcomes. For emphasis, the liberal and constructivist approaches are essential. However, the realist approach best represents this pandemic and offers the most effective basis for evaluating optimal international policy responses (Basrur and Kliem, 2020). It is also vital to state that international relations theories cannot comprehensively cover every subject aspect of the novel Coronavirus. Yet, the theory can provide educative predictions as to how nations will respond to the pandemic. It can assist in comprehending why countries and people respond to the pandemic situation the way they do, mainly through Realism. Namely, as realists would anticipate, when crises hit the globe, people do not immediately turn to international organisations, nor even the WHO or non-profit organisations, instead they run to their respective governments to make essential and urgent moves to protect and give them aid (Kliem, 2020). Typically, the sovereign state is the key actor in international politics; Basrur and Kliem (2020) claimed that states are principal actors within this anarchic global framework and utilise national self-help approaches to survive and exploit power or security (military), especially during Covid-19, which started unannounced. On the contrary, social distancing, travel and entry bans, international scapegoating, state power competition, and pharmaceutical protectionism are ubiquitous. Indeed, even in the supranational organisation, like the European Union (EU), reveals how the member states quickly abused their standards, such as the four freedoms of movement, such as products, capital, services, and residents. To illustrate, Italy was consequently far from the worst affected nation in Europe after China during the initial phase of the outbreak; in this case, the EU member states ignored Rome when it requested crisis alleviation with basic clinical supplies. Their actions consequently breached the EU's single market by declaring a prohibition on exported pharmaceutical equipment. Moreover, Rome willingly agreed to take China's and Cuba's aid by sending clinical hardware and professionals due to the absence of European solidarity. Because the Covid-19 started in Huhan in China, this negative reputation has led China to support countries affected regardless of their previous bilateral relations. Similarly, Germany shut down its boundaries with other neighbouring countries to prevent the spread of Coronavirus, as some neighbouring states also confined their residents to their homes (lockdown) (Basrur and Kliem, 2020).

In comparison, (Basrur and Kliem, 2020) stated that the United States ex-president Donald Trump attempted purchasing a German research firm close to developing Coronavirus vaccines. His action was to provide citizens of the United States exclusive access to early vaccines; this is conceivably a display of national self-interest during the Coronavirus pandemic. Notably, the dismay of neoliberal institutionalists is noteworthy to mention how minimal the WHO performs in the outbreak of the crisis. For instance, in Singapore, the WHO mainly noted for applauding the

exemplary (and unilateral) actions that Singapore used, prohibiting foreign persons from entering or keeping them to their homes very early on. The most compelling argument is that global cooperation comes effortlessly amid harmony—yet Covid-19 shows us again that such cooperation between countries is much harder to achieve.

Discussion of Findings

Most importantly, there ought to be no surprise that the pandemic outbreak reaction has affected international relations between nations, which can be positive and solidified by this pandemic; others have deteriorated in instances where nations have different political beliefs and practices. Furthermore, it is undeniably true that the Covid-19 has left numerous nations devastated, wherein some countries are battling to respond to it accurately. But it is also true that other nations intentionally or unintentionally utilise this disaster to strengthen their international relationships (Mngomezulu, 2020). For instance, Cuba has a long history of supporting other countries with medical assistance in times like this. Nonetheless, this is what international relations refer to as health internationalism. Subsequently, Cuba sent medical practitioners to several nations globally to support those in need, such as South Africa, Venezuela, Qatar, and Italy. Over 200 surgeons who are experts in different medical fields arrived in the respective territories. In that sense, the Coronavirus pandemic has sustained relationships between these states (Mngomezulu, 2020).

Furthermore, other nations also utilised the COVID-19 outbreak to reinforce their political ties. Following this, Madagascar experienced good reception in other African countries regarding its publication that it has an effective cure for the virus, like Tanzania, Guinea-Bissau, and Congo-Brazzaville. Meanwhile, South Africa then again offered to help with the clinical testing of this remedy. These are some occasions where the COVID-19 implications have designed a space for nations and people to cooperate. Correspondingly, different states are also shared data, material, financial resources, and medical expertise. For instance, the United States Government contributed thousands of ventilators to South Africa (Mngomezulu, 2020). According to Mngomezulu (2020), these are commendable actions that enhance and maintain international relations globally. Although while it shows that the Coronavirus outbreak positively affected international relations, there are cases where these relations are also negatively impacted. Comparatively, the COVID-19 adversely affected international relations. Another vital factor to note is that some of these relations were weak even before the outbreak. Yet what occurred is that they have exacerbated during the times of COVID-19. For instance, many nations did not welcome Cuba's good gesture or clinical internationalism. If anything, it has impacted further disintegration of relations between some governments and Cuba.

Consequently, President Trump's administration criticised the participated countries that acknowledged Cuban medical practitioners. He blamed Cuba for benefiting from the Covid outbreak

and urged other countries to decline their medical support. Another political concern is the allegation levelled by President Trump's administration against both China and Russia, blaming them for moving forward to cooperate in spreading misleading narratives over the Covid-19 outbreak. At the same time, President Trump cannot validate this accusation claiming that the disease originated from a Chinese laboratory that he could not further validate with more information. Precisely, given the devastating nature of the Covid-19, one could anticipate international leaders to set their political differences aside and cooperate towards finding a powerful remedy while keeping the spread of the virus rate to a minimum (Mngomezulu, 2020).

3 Conclusion

The author looked at the possible outcomes of the Coronavirus outbreak on the people's health and countries. It also emphasised the reluctance of nations to cooperate and the policies several countries embraced globally to mitigate the spread of the virus. For example, people should wear masks, PCR tests, unessential travel restrictions, quarantine, lockdown, and closing unessential shops. Simultaneously, it further illustrated the challenges developing/emerging countries face in vaccine distribution; how Europe and America purchased the vaccine with few to no doses left for the other nations. The relative deficiency of global health cooperation during the pandemic is distressing as global political leaders should see urgent risks as warnings to their countries and react immediately as the problem came into the limelight. Furthermore, international participation and coordination are needed to resolve the current economic and global crisis caused by the Covid – 19. While some countries such as Cuba can control their borders efficiently and accordingly increment the chances of protecting their citizens and successfully reducing the negative consequences that the Coronavirus brings along, yet most countries are far from achieving that (Fazal, 2020; Kebede, 2020).

Fazal (2020) further added that given how much global trade adds to the international economy, business and employment depend on merchandise and individuals' movements. Therefore, political leaders representing the people will either need to accept economic crises globally or find approaches to continue to make travel safe and comfortable instead of creating lockdowns that affect individual health and human rights. Finally, the Coronavirus is here to stay if world leaders do not cooperate to find a general solution and reduce vaccine distribution inequality.

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